

Online Appendix for Aggregating Privacy-Conscious DERs for Grid Service Provision

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This document serves as the electronic companion of the paper ‘‘Aggregating Privacy-Conscious DERs for Grid Service Provision’’. Appendix A presents a quick summary of the privacy-protection algorithm used in Section II-B, Appendix B shows the convexity of the approximate mutual information function used in Section II-B, and Appendix C presents the gradients for the optimisation problem in Section III.

APPENDIX A MUTUAL INFORMATION AS A FUNCTION OF THE GRID LOAD

This appendix summarises the method to formulate mutual information (MI) as a function of the grid load, instead of the probability distribution functions (PDFs) of the random variable pair (X_l, Y_l) and its marginals¹. The MI function for discrete random variables given by

$$I(X_l; Y_l) := \sum_{x_l \in \mathcal{X}_l} \sum_{y_l \in \mathcal{Y}_l} p_{X_l, Y_l}(x_l, y_l) \log \frac{p_{X_l, Y_l}(x_l, y_l)}{p_{X_l}(x_l)p_{Y_l}(y_l)}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

is a convex function of the PDFs of (X_l, Y_l) and its marginals. Assuming that (X_l, Y_l) is a random process that is independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.), and that X_l is known for the next T time steps, its MI at time t for a sequence of K historical observations and T control actions, $I(X_l^{[\hat{T}]}; Y_l^{[\hat{T}]})$, $\hat{T} = t + T - 1$, can be approximated by estimating the PDF of (X_l, Y_l) and its marginals using the histogram method:

$$p_{X_l, Y_l}(x_l^i, y_l^j) \approx a_l^{ij} + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} z_{l,\tau}^{ij}, \quad p_{Y_l}(y_l^j) \approx b_l^j + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} \sum_{k=1}^m z_{l,\tau}^{kj},$$

where a_l, b_l are constants that count the relative frequency of $(X_l = x_l, Y_l = y_l)$, and $(Y_l = y_l)$ over the K historical observations used to estimate the PDFs, respectively, $N_\varepsilon := K + T + mn\varepsilon$, and ε is the additive smoothing scalar constant. An approximate for the MI is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I(X_l^{[\hat{T}]}; Y_l^{[\hat{T}]}) &\approx \tilde{I}(X_l^{[\hat{T}]}; Y_l^{[\hat{T}]}) \\ &:= \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \left(a_l^{ij} + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} z_{l,\tau}^{ij} \right) \times \left\{ \log \left(a_l^{ij} + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} z_{l,\tau}^{ij} \right) - \log \left(b_l^j + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} \sum_{k=1}^m z_{l,\tau}^{kj} \right) - \log c_l^i \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where c_l counts the relative frequency of $(X_l = x_l)$ over $K + T$ time steps. (A.2) is now a non-linear and non-convex function of the variables $z_{l,\tau}$. Simplifying the approximation by replacing the logarithms with their first-order Taylor expansions around their constants and letting $\nu := 1/\log_e 2$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{I}(X_l^{[\hat{T}]}; Y_l^{[\hat{T}]}) &\approx \tilde{I}(\mathbf{z}_l) \\ &:= \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \left(a_l^{ij} + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} z_{l,\tau}^{ij} \right) \times \left\{ \log \frac{a_l^{ij}}{b_l^j c_l^i} + \frac{\nu}{a_l^{ij} N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} z_{l,\tau}^{ij} - \frac{\nu}{b_l^j N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} \sum_{k=1}^m z_{l,\tau}^{kj} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

which can now be solved in a mixed-integer quadratic program. Note that (A.3) can be bounded by a value ω by setting $\varepsilon \geq K/(\omega\nu^{-1} - mn)$, ensuring that the logarithms are expanded sufficiently away from zero. Refer to the paper by Chin et al.¹ for further details.

¹J. X. Chin, T. Tinoco De Rubira, and G. Hug, ‘‘Privacy-protecting energy management unit through model-distribution predictive control,’’ in *IEEE Trans. on Smart Grid*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3084–3093, 2017.

APPENDIX B
PROOF OF CONVEXITY FOR MI APPROXIMATE

We show that (A.3) is convex with respect to the variables $\mathbf{z}_{l,\tau}$ with relaxed binary constraints, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{z}_{l,\tau} \in [0, 1]^{m \times n}$. Hence, (8) is a convex optimisation problem by algebraic manipulation. Let $\mathcal{W} := \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$, $\mathcal{W}^{[2]} := \{B \subseteq \mathcal{W} \mid |B| = 2\}$ be the set of 2-subsets of set \mathcal{W} , and w_1 and w_2 be the first and second element of each 2-subset B . Rewriting (A.3) in the following form,

$$\tilde{I}(X_l^{[\hat{T}]}; Y_l^{[\hat{T}]}) = \mathbf{z}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{A} \mathbf{z} + d \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \overbrace{\frac{\nu}{N_\varepsilon^2} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\prod_{i=1}^m a_l^{ij} b_l^j \right)^{-1} \left\{ \sum_{B \in \mathcal{W}^{[2]}} \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq w_1, w_2}}^m a_l^{ij} \left[\sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} \left(a_l^{w_2j} z_{l,\tau}^{w_1j} - a_l^{w_1j} z_{l,\tau}^{w_2j} \right) \right]^2 \right\}}^{\mathbf{z}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{z}} + \\ &\quad \underbrace{\frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \left(z_{l,\tau}^{ij} \log \frac{a_l^{ij}}{b_l^j c_l^i} \right)}_{\mathbf{A} \mathbf{z}} + \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \left(a_l^{ij} \log \frac{a_l^{ij}}{b_l^j c_l^i} \right)}_d, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

it can be seen that (A.3) is convex if and only if $\mathbf{z}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{z}$ in (B.1) is convex, *i.e.*, \mathbf{H} is positive semi-definite. Let

$$P(m, n, T) := \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\prod_{i=1}^m a_l^{ij} b_l^j \right)^{-1} \left\{ \sum_{B \in \mathcal{W}^{[2]}} \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq w_1, w_2}}^m a_l^{ij} \left[\sum_{\tau=t}^{\hat{T}} \left(a_l^{w_2j} z_{l,\tau}^{w_1j} - a_l^{w_1j} z_{l,\tau}^{w_2j} \right) \right]^2 \right\}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Given the definitions¹ $N_\varepsilon > a_l^{ij} > 0$, and $\sum_{i=1}^m a_l^{ij} = b_l^j$, it follows that $P(m, n, T) \geq 0$ and \mathbf{H} is positive semi-definite for all combinations of $m \geq 1$, $n \geq 1$ and $T \geq 1$, implying that (A.3) is convex with respect to $z_{l,\tau}$ (but not strongly convex) for all $m \geq 1$, $n \geq 1$ and $T \geq 1$. Note that in some cases, there exist values of a_l^{ij} such that $\sum_{\tau=1}^{\hat{T}} a_l^{w_2j} z_{l,\tau}^{w_1j} = \sum_{\tau=1}^{\hat{T}} a_l^{w_1j} z_{l,\tau}^{w_2j}$ for some $B \in \mathcal{W}^{[2]}$, with $\mathbf{z} \neq 0$ resulting in $P(m, n, T) = 0$, *e.g.*, when all a_l^{ij} are initialised with the same value. \square

APPENDIX C
GRADIENTS FOR THE OPTIMISATION PROBLEM

The objective function for the optimisation problem (10) is given by

$$f(y_l, \mathbf{z}_l) = \sum_{l=1}^N \left\{ \|y_l - y_l^{ref}\|_2^2 + \mu_l \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \left(a_l^{ij} + \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} z_l^{ij} \right) \times \left(\log \frac{a_l^{ij}}{b_l^j c_l^i} + \frac{\nu}{a_l^{ij} N_\varepsilon} z_l^{ij} - \frac{\nu}{b_l^j N_\varepsilon} \sum_{k=1}^m z_l^{kj} \right) \right\} + \frac{\sigma_1}{2} \left\| \left(\sum_{l=1}^N y_l \right) - \bar{y} \right\|_2^2 + \frac{\sigma_2}{2} \|\mathbf{h}\|_2^2. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

By replacing y_l with $x_l + s_l^+ - s_l^-$, the gradients for (C.1) at time instance t can be obtained by taking its partial derivatives:

$$\nabla_{s_{l,t}^+} f(y_l, \mathbf{z}_l) = 2(x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^- - y_{l,t}^{ref}) + \sigma_1 \left[\sum_{l=1}^N (x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^-) - \bar{y}_t \right] + \sigma_2 s_{l,t-1}^+ \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$\nabla_{s_{l,t}^-} f(y_l, \mathbf{z}_l) = -2(x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^- - y_{l,t}^{ref}) - \sigma_1 \left[\sum_{l=1}^N (x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^-) - \bar{y}_t \right] + \sigma_2 s_{l,t-1}^- \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$\nabla_{z_{l,t}^{ij}} f(y_l, \mathbf{z}_l) = \mu_l \left[\frac{1}{N_\varepsilon} \log \frac{a_{l,t}^{ij}}{b_{l,t}^j c_{l,t}^i} + \frac{2\nu}{a_{l,t}^{ij} N_\varepsilon^2} z_{l,t-1}^{ij} - \frac{2\nu}{b_{l,t}^j N_\varepsilon^2} \sum_{k=1}^m z_{l,t-1}^{kj} \right] + \sigma_2 z_{l,t-1}^{ij} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

For the distributed online gradient descent algorithm, the interim solutions $\tilde{s}_{l,t}^+$ and $\tilde{s}_{l,t}^-$ are computed by further replacing $\sum_{l=1}^N (x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^-)$ with \hat{y} :

$$\tilde{s}_{l,t}^+ = s_{l,t-1}^+ - r \left\{ 2(x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^- - y_{l,t}^{ref}) + \sigma_1 [\hat{y} - \bar{y}_t] + \sigma_2 s_{l,t-1}^+ \right\} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

$$\tilde{s}_{l,t}^- = s_{l,t-1}^- - r \left\{ -2(x_{l,t-1} + s_{l,t-1}^+ - s_{l,t-1}^- - y_{l,t}^{ref}) - \sigma_1 [\hat{y} - \bar{y}_t] + \sigma_2 s_{l,t-1}^- \right\} \quad (\text{C.6})$$